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On the citation relationship between industry funded and publicly funded Canadian Food Research publications

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Introduction

Access to research funding is crucial for researchers and research organizations. It increases research capacity (Huang & Huang, 2018) which typically leads to increased scholarly output and impact facilitating the formation of professional networks (Murray et al., 2016; Hicks & Katz, 2011; Auranen & Nieminen, 2010; Contrandriopoulos et al., 2018).

Researchers operate in funding environments that can be restrictive, forcing them to adapt by selecting research problems that will increase their chances of receiving funding as opposed to pursuing their own research interests (Laudel, 2006). There is a high heterogeneity of funding configurations with private, public, non-profit, and university funders jointly supporting research projects (Aagard et al., 2021). These regimes can thus guide science in certain direction, and possibly generate or sustain ignorance. A perhaps unintended consequence of an overconcentration of research funding is that some science doesn't get done. This concentration, once coupled with the reliance on industry, risks leading to the overproduction of research aligning with industrial interests, or worse, to maintaining our collective ignorance (Greyson, 2019).

Biases in research funding received a lot of attention in the scientific community (Banal-Estañol et al., 2019; Guthrie et al., 2019). This bias is often explained through the idea that funders are more likely to fund research that benefits their goals or initiatives (Krimsky 2013). Industry funded research tends to have an industry favoured outcome in comparison to non-profit funded research in the same area (Als-Nielsen et al., 2003; Yaphe et al., 2001). The pharmaceutical and tobacco industries are the primary examples of industry favoured results in research, with many studies facilitating research outcomes based on industry focuses (Djulbegovic et al., 2000; Kjaergard & Als-Nielsen, 2002; Mitchell et al., 2020). That being said, bias in research is not necessarily a distinctly industry specific issue. A study conducted by Larivière et al. (2018) suggests that governments often sponsor research that will help to provide evidence that supports initiatives and mandates, further emphasizing bias in project selection for funded research.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this work-in-progress is to provide empirical insights on the dynamics of food science research funding in Canada, with a particular focus on the funding source and its relationship to the distribution of resources across institutions, researchers and research topics. More specifically, we aim to answer the following research questions:

RQ1. How concentrated is research funding by industry and government agencies at the level of institutions and researchers?

RQ2. How is funding by different sources distributed in the food research network?

RQ3. What is the intent of citations (supportive or critical) between industry-funded research and publicly funded (or not funded) research?

This study is to our knowledge the first to use bibliometric approach to understand the funding landscape of Canadian food science.

Data & Methods

We collected from the Web of Science (WoS) all publications published in 2008 onwards published in one of 322 agriculture and food science related journals (based on relevant WoS Subject Categories), with at least 1 author with an institutional affiliation in Canada. To eliminate false positives caused by the multidisciplinary coverage of some journals, we narrowed that the publication set to those containing one of 64 search terms selected by the research team. The resulting dataset includes 13,387 publications. We collected the organizations mentioned in the funding acknowledgements and classified them in five groups (industry, government, government funding agencies, universities, and other). In total, 7,542 publications had at least one funder. The number of publications by funder category is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of publications by funding source category.

Funding source category	Publications	
	N	%
Government funding agency	5,152	38.5
Industry	2,892	21.6
Government	2,592	19.4
University	1,987	14.8
Other	360	2.7

We used Gephi to visualize the direct citation network of food research and identify publications clusters using the Louvain algorithm (Blondel et al. 2008), which we used to analyze the distribution of papers by funding sources. We used the Open Alex paper level classification of topics to identify the main topics represented in each cluster (RQ2).

In order to investigate the intent of citations between the publications (RQ3) we used scite citation data (Nicholson et al. 2021) which indicates whether a citation is supporting, contrasting, or mentioning a cited paper. Given the funding data above and additional funding attribution data from Crossref, we looked at the distribution of citations by type within and across two funding groups (presented in Table 2): research that has been publicly funded only (18,574 publications) and research that has industry funding (7,116 publications). We then used

two-sided t-tests between each citation pattern to determine whether there were any statistically significant differences in citation behaviour per group.

Table 2. Distribution of citation intent by citation pattern.

Citation Pattern	Total			Supporting			Contrasting		
	μ	works	cites	μ	works	cites	μ	works	cites
Industry to Industry	2.31	794	1,841	7.44	372	2,770	6.56	100	597
Public to Public	1.83	3,231	5,928	1.86	958	1,788	1.75	177	276
Industry to Public	1.72	543	934	4.02	982	244	3.41	59	188
Public to Public	1.62	710	1,153	3.8	208	792	3.74	49	161
Industry to Any	5.02	1,442	7,252	4.99	1,243	6,212	5.52	324	1,325
Public to Any	3.85	6,345	24,489	1.83	3,149	5,787	2.17	548	917
Any to Industry	1.76	2,700	4,767	5.52	795	4,396	5.25	206	961
Any to Public	1.70	7,166	12,238	2.18	1,927	4,208	2.08	397	685

Results

Figure 1 shows that about 5% of organizations publish 80% of the work and obtain 80% of the funding, and that industry funding is more concentrated than other sources of funding.

Figure 1. Concentration of research funding at the institutional level.

We now look into the distribution of funding across food research publications clusters which are represented in Figure 2. In Table 3, we use the most frequent topics to describe the research areas covered by each cluster. We used level 2 topics from Open Alex for this purpose. Then Table 2 also displays the share of publications from each cluster that received different types of funding. We find that industry funding is concentrated in cluster 1 (food production) and cluster 4 (animal production).

Figure 2. Network of publications based on direct citations.

Table 3. Topics, number of publications and funding sources of the research clusters.

Cluster	Topics	Pubs	Funding source		
			Industry	Gov.	Funding Agencies
1	ammonia, antioxidant, arid, food contaminant, food industry, food intake, food preservation, food processing, hydrocortisone, hydrogen administration	3407	37%	29%	38%
2	baby food, canola, coefficient of determination, deformation (meteorology), germ, germination, inhalation, inhibitory postsynaptic potential, inoculation, insect	3146	16%	17%	42%
3	agency (philosophy), biological warfare, clenbuterol, consumption (sociology), detection limit, developing country, development studies, extraction (chemistry), fatty acid, feces	897	16%	21%	33%
4	animal production, camelina, carbohydrate metabolism, cecum, crypt, embryo, food intake, forage, hydrolysis, hydrostatic pressure	788	40%	17%	28%
5	aqueous solution, carbohydrate, continuous stirred-tank reactor, fatty acid, fermentation, gene, glucan, glutaraldehyde, gluten, glycerol	424	17%	24%	52%

Turning to our third research question, we investigate the citation relationships between papers based on their funding sources. Our analysis shows that citation patterns reflect the consolidation of funding in industry as well. Notably, we observed one significant pattern, Industry funded research tends to give and receive more citations irrespective of type and tends to give itself more citations than publicly funded works cite themselves (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Industry funded research (n=1442) tends give more citations than publicly funded research (n=6345) does ($p < 0.00$). Industry funded research (n=794) tends to cite itself more than publicly funded research does (n=3231) ($p=0.00$). N indicates number of publications.

When examining group support tendencies, we observe the same trend that industry funded publications tend to be more supported and give more supporting citations (see Figure 4). However, we also observe that while across group support is similar, industry tends to support itself much more than public research funds itself. This same trend can be seen in Figure 5 which outlines critical citation behaviour. The patterns observed here indicate that research with industry funding could be both better quality and more novel (attracting supporting citations) as well as riskier (attracting more criticism). While the effects are statistically significant indicating that this is not an outcome of industry funded works having more citations, the sample size is relatively low and future work should look at this on a larger set of publications.

Figure 4. On the left: Industry funded research (n=1243) tends give more supporting citations than publicly funded research (n=3149) does ($p < 0.00$). Industry funded research (n=795) tends receive more supporting citations than publicly funded research (n=1927) does ($p < 0.00$). On the right: Industry funded research (n=372) tends give more supporting citations to itself than publicly funded research does to itself (n=958) ($p < 0.00$). Industry funded research (n=244) and publicly funded research (n=208) do not have a significant difference in cross group supporting behaviour ($p=0.59$). N indicates number of publications.

Figure 5. On the left: Industry funded research (n=324) tends give more critical citations than publicly funded research (n=548) does ($p < 0.00$) and industry funded research (n=206) tends receive more criticisms than publicly funded research (n=367) does ($p < 0.00$). On the right: Industry funded research (n=206) tends to criticize itself more than publicly funded research criticizes itself. (n=548) ($p=1.114708949118939e-23$). Industry funded research (n=56) doesn't give more critical citations to publicly funded research than publicly funded research (n=49) gives to industry funded work ($p=0.90$). N indicates number of publications.

Discussion & Conclusion

Our results illustrate that there is a higher incidence of supporting and contrasting citations given to industry publications. This finding is a leading indicator of how novelty and risk are both at play with industry funded research. Disagreement is not uncommon and is even desirable in research (Lamers et al., 2021). Supported publications tend to be sufficiently novel in their ideas, resulting in other researchers supporting their ideas or even finding the same results. This is a common process in academic discourse, with researchers aiming for competing results with different methods and results as a means of publishing rivalrous discourse (Greenberg & Robins, 1986). Opposing positions and viewpoints in industrial findings further emphasize Tannen's (2002) argument that "ritualized adversativeness" in academic research promotes disagreement and opposition through agonism. Nonetheless, critical citations,

especially arising in aggregate from a group, can indicate that the group is engaging in riskier research because they are making more tentative statements that can be disputed.

Novelty and risk seem to be more present in industrial work than publicly funded work, with the latter being more conservative in the citations it makes and receives. Our observations show that industrial work is more supported (and self-supported) and criticized (and self-criticized) than publicly funded research. This may be because often industrial research and publicly funded research on the same topics tend to have different research objectives, resulting in different outcomes (Golder & McCambridge, 2021). There are also significant risks and criticism that come with taking industry funding, as it can fuel tension and animosity from their peers regarding researcher's capabilities as well as their integrity as an academic (Gillison, 2019).

Industry funding functions as a double-edged sword for researchers – as Hottenrott and Thorwarth (2011) found that large amounts of funding from industry reduces research output for academics, but industry funded research is also more likely to improve both quality of research and patent citation impact. Industry funding is also an integral source for knowledge creation and sharing, as many industries are not only responsible for funding research, but also conferences, research labs and institutions, lectures, and journals (Nestle, 2001).

We should emphasize the importance of concentration of industry funding, and how it affects engagement and impact based on distribution. Partnerships with industries for research funding are not meant to fund all research – therefore it makes sense that industrial funding is concentrated in certain disciplines. Industrial distribution is often selective, with a general focus on the epistemic effects of funded research such as productivity, research potential, and ground-breaking innovation (Aagard, Kladakis, & Neilsen, 2020). Although these are the motives behind funding concentration, that does not necessarily mean that this will be the given outcome, as many heavily funded and well-established researchers have proven to have minimal positive research impacts (Mongeon et al., 2016).

However, there is still a lot that is unknown when it comes to industrial research concentration and impact in the food science discipline. Future research could examine disagreement at the community level to understand how researchers in specific disciplines interact with industry funded research. In addition, the consolidation of novelty and risk in food science is an interesting finding that could be further pursued in other research areas that are heavily influenced by industrial research, such as gambling, medicine, and pharmacy. This research could provide valuable insight into whether criticism and support within groups are self-supported or self-criticized, or if they are indicative of dynamics within publicly funded and industrial research groups such as competition between labs or individual researchers.

Based on our findings, further work may seek to better understand the citation behaviour between funded and non-funded research in food science. Can we observe citation differences in industry and publicly funded research on the same topics? Examination at this level could detect visible competition patterns from researchers with different types of institutional funding and help us to better understand potential topical preference biases based on industrial funding, and topics that are understudied due to lack of support and funding restraints.

References

- Aagaard, K., Kladakis, A., & Nielsen, M. (2020). Concentration or dispersal of research funding? *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 117-149.
- Aagaard, K., Mongeon, P., Ramos-Vielba, I., & Thomas, D. (2021). Getting to the bottom of research funding: Acknowledging the complexity of funding dynamics. *PloS One*, 16(5), E0251488.
- Als-Neilsen, B., Chen, W., Gluud, C., & Kjaergard, L. (2003). Association of Funding and Conclusions in Randomized Drug Trials: A Reflection of Treatment or Effect or Adverse Events? *The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 290(4), 921-28.
- Auranen O, Nieminen M. (2010) University research funding and publication performance—An international comparison. *Research Policy*. 39(6):822–34.
- Banal-Estañol, A., Macho-Stadler, I., & Pérez-Castrillo, D. (2019). Evaluation in research funding agencies: Are structurally diverse teams biased against? *Research Policy*, 48(7), 1823-1840.
- Blondel, V., Guillaume, J., Lambiotte, R., & Lefebvre, E. (2008). Fast unfolding of communities in large networks. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics*, 2008(10), P10008-12.
- Contrandriopoulos, D., Larouche, C., & Duhoux, A. (2018). Evaluating Academic Research Networks. *Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation*, 33(1), 69-89.
- Djulgovic, B., Lacevic, M., Cantor, A., Fields, K., Bennett, C., Adams, J., Kudere, N., & Lyman, G. (2000). The uncertainty principle and industry-sponsored research. *The Lancet (British Edition)*, 356(9230), 635-638.
- Gillison, F. (2019). Reflections from a casualty of the food industry research funding debate. *BMJ (Online)*, 365, L2034.
- Golder, S., & McCambridge, J. (2021). Alcohol, cardiovascular disease and industry funding: A co-authorship network analysis of systematic reviews. *Social Science & Medicine (1982)*, 289, 114450.
- Greenberg, D., & Robins, P. (1986). The changing role of social experiments in policy analysis. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 5(2), 340-362.
- Greyson, D. (2019). The Social Informatics of Ignorance. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 70(4), 412-415.
- Guthrie, S., Rodriguez Rincon, D., McInroy, G., Ioppolo, B., & Gunashekar, S. (2019). Measuring bias, burden and conservatism in research funding processes. *F1000 Research*, 8, 851.
- Hicks, D., & Katz, J. (2011). Equity and Excellence in Research Funding. *Minerva*, 49(2), 137-151.

- Hottenrott, H., & Thorwarth, S. (2011). Industry Funding of University Research and Scientific Productivity. *Kyklos (Basel)*, 64(4), 534-555.
- Huang, M, & Huang, M. (2018). An analysis of global research funding from subject field and funding agencies perspectives in the G9 countries. *Scientometrics*, 115(2), 833-847.
- Kjaergard, L., & Als-Nielsen, B. (2002). Association between competing interests and authors' conclusions: Epidemiological study of randomised clinical trials published in the BMJ. *BMJ*, 325(7358), 249-252.
- Krimsky, S. (2013). Do Financial Conflicts of Interest Bias Research? An Inquiry into the "Funding Effect" Hypothesis. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 38(4), 566-587.
- Lamers, W., Boyack, K., Larivière, V., Sugimoto, C., Van Eck, N., Waltman, L., & Murray, D. (2021). Investigating disagreement in the scientific literature. *ELife*, 10, ELife, 2021-12-24, Vol.10.
- Larivière, V., Macaluso, B., Mongeon, P., Siler, K., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2018). Vanishing industries and the rising monopoly of universities in published research. *PLoS One*, 13(8).
- Laudel, G. (2006). The art of getting funded: How scientists adapt to their funding conditions. *Science & Public Policy*, 33(7), 489-504.
- Mitchell, G., Lesch, M., & McCambridge, J. (2020). Alcohol Industry Involvement in the Moderate Alcohol and Cardiovascular Health Trial. *American Journal of Public Health (1971)*, 110(4), 485-488.
- Mongeon, P., Brodeur, C., Beaudry, C., & Larivière, V. (2016). Concentration of research funding leads to decreasing marginal returns. *Research Evaluation*, Rvw007.
- Murray, D., Morris, D., Lavoie, C., Leavitt, P., MacIsaac, H., Masson, M., & Villard, M. (2016). Bias in Research Grant Evaluation Has Dire Consequences for Small Universities. *PloS One*, 11(6), E0155876.
- Nestle, M. (2001). Food company sponsorship of nutrition research and professional activities: a conflict of interest? *Public Health Nutrition*, 4(5), 1015-1022.
- Nicholson, J., Mordaunt, M., Lopez, P., Uppala, A., Rosati, D., Rodrigues, N., Grabitz, P., & Rife, S. (2021). Scite: A smart citation index that displays the context of citations and classifies their intent using deep learning. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(3), 882-898.
- Tannen D. 2002. Agonism in academic discourse. *Journal of Pragmatics* 34:1651–1669.
- Yaphe, J., Edman, R., Knishkowsky, B., & Herman, J. (2001) The Association Between Funding by Commercial Interests and Study Outcome in Randomized Drug Controlled Trials. *Family Practice*, 18(12), 565-68.